

"EFFECTS OF ORGANIZING LESSONS USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN ENGLISH LESSONS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS"

Kasimova Shoiri Komiljon qizi

Asaka district of Andijan region 57th General Secondary School English teacher

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Abstract. Today, the younger generation is increasingly interested in learning foreign languages. Therefore, teaching a foreign language, including English, in secondary schools requires the use of interactive methods in the classroom. This article focuses on the effectiveness of organizing lessons using interactive methods in English classes in secondary schools.

Keywords: Method, interactive method, information and communication technologies, interactivity.

"ЭФФЕКТЫ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ УРОКОВ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ МЕТОДОВ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В СРЕДНИХ ШКОЛАХ"

Аннотация. Сегодня подрастающее поколение все больше интересуется изучением иностранных языков. Поэтому обучение иностранному языку, в том числе английскому, в общеобразовательных школах требует использования интерактивных методов на занятиях. В данной статье речь пойдет об эффективности организации уроков с использованием интерактивных методов на уроках английского языка в общеобразовательных школах.

Ключевые слова: Метод, интерактивный метод, информационно-коммуникационные технологии, интерактивность.

INTRODUCTION

Significant work is being done in our country to form an information society, to introduce the most advanced information and communication technologies in all areas. In particular, the capabilities of interactive services in this process are highly valued. The Uzbek dictionary defines the term "interactive" as based on the reception or transmission of information over a computer network. Wikipedia, on the other hand, evaluates interactivity as a concept that reveals the nature and extent of interactions between objects and is said to be used in information theory, computer science and programming, telecommunications systems, sociology, industrial design, and more. In other words, interactivity is a system of organizing the system, which is to achieve a specific goal by establishing the exchange of information between parts of the system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The interactive method is aimed at activating the acquisition of knowledge and developing personal qualities of students by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process. Using interactive methods can help increase lesson effectiveness. The main criteria of interactive education are: informal discussions, the ability to freely express and express the learning material, the small number of lectures, but the large number of seminars, the creation of opportunities for students to take initiative, small group, large group, assignment to work as a class team, written work and other methods, which are of particular importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work. One of the main directions in improving teaching methods today is the introduction of interactive teaching and learning methods. All

science teachers are increasingly using interactive methods in their teaching. As a result of using interactive methods, students develop the skills of independent thinking, analysis, drawing conclusions, expressing their opinions, defending them on the basis of them, healthy communication, discussion, debate. In the process of interactive learning, the lesson is based on the interaction of students.

RESULTS

Derived from the English word interactive, "Interact", that is, Inter - means "interaction", "act" - means action, influence, activity. Interactivity is the interaction of two people, that is, the learning process takes place in the form of a conversation, in the form of dialogue (computer communication) or on the basis of teacher-student interaction. Interaction - interaction, movement, sensitivity, occurs in student-teacher, student-student (subject-subject) conversations. The main purpose of interactive methods is to create the most favorable environment for the learning process, creating an environment for active, free, creative thinking of the student, the use of his needs, interests, inner potential. Such lessons are held in such a way that in the process, no student is left out, and has the opportunity to openly express their views on what they have heard, read and seen. There is a process of mutual exchange of views. Children develop an interest in learning, develop friendly relations. Modern interactive methods in foreign language teaching methods have been developed by scientists and have proven to be more effective than traditional methods.

DISCUSSION

Interactive methods significantly increase the knowledge potential of the learning process compared to traditional methods. Because in interactive methods, the student thinks independently and works in partnership with the teacher. With the help of modern technologies, the student plans the lesson process, engages in it according to the curriculum, chooses teaching methods jointly with the student and the teacher, participate in the discussion of the material. Students help each other. In the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries, the term "interactive" methods of education is widely used in pedagogical literature. We will try to give. "Inter" is used in the extreme sense. Interactive means a very active learning method. This group of methods allows students to think independently, be creative, and be interested in the essence of the topic. It should be noted that interactive teaching methods in Uzbekistan since ancient times in the educational process, such as discussion, debate, negotiation, observation, analysis, consultation, poetry reading, reading in the dialogue between teacher and students and between students and students. used in the forms. These methods helped students to become independent thinkers by developing their speech, thinking, reasoning, intelligence, talent, and intelligence. It is now known that interactive methods are mainly used in conducting interactive exercises. In the future, it is desirable that these methods will grow to some extent interactive technology.

CONCLUSIONS

In our opinion, the difference between this interactive method and the concept of technology can be described as follows. Interactive teaching method - implemented by each teacher at the level of available tools and their own capabilities.

At the same time, each student learns at different levels according to their motives and intellectual level. Interactive Learning Technology - Ensures that each teacher conducts the learning activities as intended for all students. In this case, each student has his own motives and

intellectual level, and masters the lesson at the intended level. Based on the study of some experiences in the practical application of interactive training, we can identify some of the factors that affect the quality and effectiveness of these trainings. They can be conditionally called organizational-pedagogical, scientific-methodical and factors related to the teacher, students, teaching aids. We need to keep in mind that they have a positive or negative impact, depending on their nature.

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